

Thermoelectric Properties of Non-Magnetic Bimetallic Noble Metals Atomic Wires

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a systematic first-principles study on electrical, thermal, and thermoelectric transport properties of non-magnetic bimetallic atomic wires of noble metals (viz., CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu) modelled in linear, and ladder topologies. Both electronic and phononic contributions to thermal conductance have been considered. To this endeavor, we have made use of the DFT-NEGF approach to compute the electronic contribution, while the phononic is calculated with the use of GULP code followed by the NEGF approach. Numerical results have been presented for different transport coefficients viz. electrical conductance G , electronic (κ_{el}) and phononic (κ_{ph}) thermal conductance, thermopower S and total figure of merit ZT in the linear response regime. As an important finding the thermoelectric figure of merit ZT found to increase many-fold times over the pristine wires; particularly AgAu wire in linear configuration is found to exhibit the maximum ZT of ≈ 3.3 at $\mu = -0.6$ eV.

Keywords

Bimetallic Atomic Wires, Electrical, Thermal, Thermoelectric, properties GULP, DFT, SIESTA

Introduction

Recent advances in Nano-fabrication and engineering tools, have provided an ability to tune the size and shape of the nanostructures in controlled manner to synthesize the novel one dimensional (1D) nanostructures such as nanowires (NWs), Nanoribbons, Nano-tubes, quantum wires etc. In particular, noble metals NWs have attracted huge research interest in various disciplinary areas of science and engineering due to their applications in the field of electronics, thermoelectric, optoelectronics, catalysts, sensors etc. On these NWs many experimental studies have been performed mainly to explore the electronic properties and emerged out with novel electrical behavior like quantized electrical conductance [1] and the signatures of the Tomonaga-Luttinger liquid behavior [2], which make their promising applications in future Nano electronics [3]. On the theoretical side, electronic [4], magnetic [5], optical [6] and transport properties [7] of ultrathin NWs have been investigated. Among interesting results, these properties have been found to be substantially varying with the type of structure (for example linear, ladder topologies etc.) as well as nature of constituent atom(s). Recently Hong et al, [8] have observed the Coulomb blockade effects in ultrathin AuAg bimetallic NWs, which rendered them useful in electrical devices and sensors applications as either single electron transistors (SETs) or Coulomb blockade thermometers. Later, it has been observed that nanosheet prepared via assembly of ultrathin AuAg NWs in the presence of the triblock copolymer Pluronic P123 can be used as the promising candidate in memory devices, since these nanosheets exhibit a write-once-read-many-times switching behavior. On the other hand, the semiconducting nature has been observed in few micron long AuAg NWs with diameter ranging from 4 to 12 nm [9]. Earlier, Enomoto et al [10], studied the effect of alloying on quantized electrical conductance of AuPd and AuAg nanocontacts. On theoretical side, Fioravante et al [11] have studied the free standing bimetallic NWs of Ag and Au in different topologies and reported significant variation in electrical behaviour with topology. Recently Kumar et al. [7] have systematically examined the electrical transport properties of ultrathin (freestanding) alloyed NWs of noble metals (Cu, Ag, Au, and Pt) using the DFT approach. Interestingly, electrical behavior were seen to be sensitive not only to the type of alloying, but also the structure of NWs. Despite extensive experimental and theoretical studies on electrical transport properties, relatively much less attention has been paid on heat transport in both pristine and alloyed NWs of noble metals. While there exists a few studies on heat transport in pristine NWs [12], the alloyed NWs remain largely unexplored.

Keeping in view the effect of alloying on electrical transport properties, in the present work we have carried out the systematic study on electrical, thermal and thermoelectric transport properties of bimetallic atomic wires of noble metals (i.e., CuAg, CuAu, and

AgAu) modelled linear and ladder topologies as shown in Fig. 1. In section 2, we describe the theoretical formalism. In section 3, simulation cell describing the device and computational parameters used in DFT and semi-empirical calculations, are presented. Numerical results and discussion are given in section 4. Finally, in section 5, we summarize the main conclusions of our work.

Objective of study

In this paper we have performed for the first time simulation study of electrical, thermal, and thermoelectric transport properties of non-magnetic bimetallic atomic wires of noble metals (viz., CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu) modelled in linear, and ladder topologies. Electronic contribution of thermal conductance is calculated using Spanish DFT code SIESTA and phononic contribution using code GULP.

Review of Literature

Like, pristine metallic NWs, the studies on bimetallic (alloy) NWs also have been boosted since the last few years with the effort to see the effect of alloying on electrical transport. Recently Hong et al, [8] have observed the Coulomb blockade effects in ultrathin AuAg bimetallic NWs, which rendered them useful in electrical devices and sensors applications as either single electron transistors (SETs) or Coulomb blockade thermometers. Later, it has been observed that nanosheet prepared via assembly of ultrathin AuAg NWs in the presence of the triblock copolymer Pluronic P123 can be used as the promising candidate in memory devices, since these nanosheets exhibit a write-once-read-many-times switching behavior. On the other hand, the semiconducting nature has been observed in few micron long AuAg NWs with diameter ranging from 4 to 12 nm [9]. Earlier, Enomoto et al [10], studied the effect of alloying on quantized electrical conductance of AuPd and AuAg nanocontacts by varying wide range of Pd and Ag concentrations, and observed a decrease in probability of appearance of $1G_0$ quantum conductance with increase in concentration. On theoretical side, Fioravante et al [11] have studied the free standing bimetallic NWs of Ag and Au in different topologies and reported the significant variation in electrical behaviour with topology. Recently Kumar et al. [7] have systematically examined the electrical transport properties of ultrathin (freestanding) alloyed NWs of noble metals (Cu, Ag, Au, and Pt) using the DFT approach. While there exists a few studies on heat transport in pristine NWs, the alloyed NWs remain largely unexplored. Keeping in view the effect of alloying on electrical transport properties, in the present work we have carried out the systematic study on thermal and thermoelectric transport properties of bimetallic atomic wires of noble metals (i.e., CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu) modelled linear and ladder topologies.

Main Text

In literature theoretically as well as experimentally electronic[4], magnetic[5], optical[6] and transport properties[7] of ultrathin NWs have been investigated. Among interesting results, these properties have been found to be substantially varying with the type of structure (for example linear, ladder topologies etc.) as well as nature of constituent atom(s). Enomoto et al[10], studied the effect of alloying on quantized electrical conductance of AuPd and AuAg nanocontacts. Fioravante et al[11] have studied the free standing bimetallic NWs of Ag and Au in different topologies and reported significant variation in electrical behaviour with topology. Recently [12] we have systematically examined the electrical transport properties of ultrathin (freestanding) alloyed NWs of noble metals (Cu, Ag, Au, and Pt) using SIESTA and GULP Code. Interestingly, we observed that electrical behavior was seen to be sensitive not only to the type of alloying, but also the structure of NWs. Keeping in view the effect of alloying on electrical transport properties, in the present work we have extended our previous study by taking different combinations of bimetallic atomic wires of noble metals (i.e. CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu) modelled in linear and ladder topologies as shown in Fig.1

2. Theoretical Formalism:

The Landauer-Büttiker approach [13–14], can be used to compute both the electronic and phononic contribution to different transport properties of Nano scale devices. This approach is exact in the coherent transport limit where inelastic scattering and phase breaking mechanism are absent. In the present study, we have used this approach, thus ignoring any inelastic scattering of carriers (electrons or phonons).

(a) Electronic Contribution:

The electrical current I and electronic thermal current Q_{el} through an atomic wire, as described in Fig.1, under both voltage gradient $\Delta\mu = \mu_L - \mu_R$ and temperature gradient $\Delta T = T_L - T_R$ are defined, respectively, as [15]

$$I = \frac{2e}{h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau_{el}(E) [f(E, \mu_L, T_L) - f(E, \mu_R, T_R)] dE, \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{el} = \frac{2}{h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau_{el}(E) (E - \mu) [f(E, \mu_L, T_L) - f(E, \mu_R, T_R)] dE. \quad (2)$$

Here, $f(E, \mu, T) = \left[1 + \exp\left(\frac{E - \mu}{k_B T}\right) \right]^{-1}$ is the Fermi function, describing the occupation of single electron orbitals in the left (right) electron reservoir at chemical potential μ_L (μ_R) and temperature T_L (T_R), and $\tau_{el}(E)$ is the electron transmission function which is calculated using the NEGF method [15-16]. The energy of electrons is measured relative to the average chemical potential, $\mu = (\mu_L + \mu_R)/2$. In the limit of infinitesimal $\Delta\mu$ and ΔT , one can restrict to the linear response regime and the electronic thermoelectric coefficients [17], viz. electrical conductance G , thermopower S , and electronic thermal conductance κ_{el} can be obtained from Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively, as

$$G(\mu, T) = \frac{2e^2}{h} N_0(\mu, T), \quad (3)$$

$$S(\mu, T) = -\frac{N_1(\mu, T)}{eTN_0(\mu, T)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\kappa_{el} = \frac{2}{hT} \left\{ N_2(\mu, T) - \frac{N_1^2(\mu, T)}{N_0(\mu, T)} \right\}, \quad (5)$$

Where $N_m(\mu, T)$ is given by

$$N_m(\mu, T) = \frac{2}{h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau_{el}(E) (E - \mu)^m \left(\frac{-\partial f(E, \mu, T)}{\partial E} \right) dE. \quad (6)$$

(b) Phononic Contribution:

As for the electronic contribution, the part of heat current carried by phonons can be calculated using the Landauer-Büttiker approach [18] as

$$Q_{ph} = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{ph}(E) E [n(E, T_L) - n(E, T_R)] dE. \quad (7)$$

The corresponding phononic thermal conductance κ_{ph} in the linear response regime is then given by

$$\kappa_{ph} = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^{\infty} \tau_{ph}(E) E \left[\frac{\partial n(E, T)}{\partial E} \right] dE, \quad (8)$$

where $\tau_{ph}(E)$ is the phonon transmission function and $n(E, T) = \left[\exp \left(\frac{E}{k_B T} \right) - 1 \right]^{-1}$, represents the distribution of phonons in each electrode. Finally, the total figure of merit, which measures thermoelectric efficiency of device, can be calculated as

$$ZT = \frac{GS^2}{\kappa_{el} + \kappa_{ph}} T. \quad (9)$$

3. Wire Model and Computational Details-We have considered, two different topologies viz. Linear and ladder according to spatial distribution of atoms as shown in Figs. 1(a-b). The super-cell used to model the device configuration for linear, and ladder topologies is made from a conventional unit cell (UC) represented by the violet-dotted box in Figs. 1(a-b). In linear topology, a super-cell of 20 atoms, divided into three basic parts as left electrode, scattering region, and right electrode containing 6, 8, and 6 atoms respectively, is used (see, Fig. 1(a)). Similarly, the ladder topology (see Fig. 1(b)) is modelled by a super-cell of 40 atoms with 16 atoms in the scattering region and 12 atoms each in the left and right electrodes. The wire atoms in each topology are placed in the x-z plane, with wire length and transport direction taken along the z axis. A vacuum gap of 25 Å between neighboring wires in the transverse (x and y) directions has been used to prevent interactions between adjacent unit cells. Also, the size of the super cell is chosen optimally to meet all the requirements of TransSIESTA. Having selected the UC for each topology, we first calculate the structural and electronic properties of bimetallic wires using the DFT approach as implemented in the SIESTA code. The cutoff radii r_c for the s, p, d, and f channels used here to generate the pseudo-potential is same as that used in our recent DFT study on pristine noble metal wires (see Table 1 of Ref. [12]). Exchange-correlation energy is approximated within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) according to PBEsol [19] parameterization. The convergence tolerance for total energy is chosen as 10^{-6} eV.

Figure 1: Ball-stick representation of super-cell for bimetallic atomic wires in (a) linear, and (b) ladder topologies. The super-cell is divided in three main components for transport analysis: semi-infinite left and right electrodes and scattering region (device). In each case, box drawn with dashed line represents conventional unit cell used to make the super cell.

After being optimized the structure of bimetallic wires, the electronic transport properties are then calculated using the NEGF approach, within the Landauer-Büttiker formalism as implemented in the TransSIESTA[20] module of SIESTA package [21]. The electron transmission function $\tau_{el}(E)$ thus obtained is used in Eqs. (3)-(6) to compute the electronic contribution to the thermoelectric coefficients. The corresponding phononic transport properties are calculated via semi-empirical potential based code GULP [22] where inter-atomic potential is obtained by the embedded atom method (EAM).

Electrical and Thermal Transport:In the panels (a)-(c) and (d)-(f) of Figs. 2 and 4, we have reported the numerical results of the equilibrium (i.e., when $\Delta T = \Delta \mu = 0$) electronic $\tau_{el}(E)$ and phononic $\tau_{ph}(E)$ transmission functions, respectively, for linear and ladder topologies. Since these are the key ingredient of our calculations, their behavior entirely determine the electrical and thermal transport parameters. Clearly, both $\tau_{el}(E)$ and $\tau_{ph}(E)$ have shown a significant dependence not only on the type of alloying but also on topology. A direct comparison among $\tau_{el}(E_F)$ reveals that all wires in ladder, and CuAu wire in linear topology exhibit metallic behavior, whereas the remaining wires are semiconducting in nature. Interestingly, in comparison with pristine wires in linear topology, alloying of Cu and Au with Ag, change their nature from metallic to

Result and Discussion

semiconducting. At zero bias, we find that the electrical conductance G ($= G_0 \tau_{el}(E_F$; $G_0 = 2e^2/h$, is the basic quantum of conductance) is G_0 and $2G_0$ for metallic wires in linear and ladder topologies, respectively, thus suggested ballistic electron transport in these wires. Just as $\tau_{el}(E)$, $\tau_{ph}(E)$ for alloyed wires also shows a remarkable difference both in the Debye energy and the number of phonon conduction channels from pristine wires of their constituent atoms.

Linear Topology:At first, G as a function of T is computed for different chemical potential μ of electrodes by using $\tau_{el}(E)$ (shown in Figs. 2 (a-c)). Its numerical results for the case of $\mu = 0$ eV (measured with respect to E_F) is plotted in Fig. 3. Apparently, in contrast to CuAg and AgAu wires, CuAu wire shows a unusual non-monotonic T -dependence of G , first it decreases with T (as in a metal), then increases continuously after getting a broad minima at $T \sim 170$ K. Interestingly, G for pristine wires of Cu and Au has not seen such type of behavior, thus suggesting the alloying effect. Further, to examine the electron heat transport in wires, we calculate κ_{el} over the investigated T at different μ by using Eqs. (5) and (6). For $\mu = 0$, its T -dependence for different wires is shown in Fig. 2(g). Although, in comparison with pristine wires, CuAu wire preserve the metallic nature but κ_{el} is significantly departed from the linear T -dependence, particularly in low temperature regime. Recently, Jariwala et al. [23] have also reported a linear temperature dependence of κ_{el} for pristine Au wire in different topologies using the BoltzTrap code. Moreover, we find that alloying reduces κ_{el} in all wires with at least 24 % decrease w.r.t the average κ_{el} of the constituent's pristine wires. Just as κ_{el} , κ_{ph} is calculated with the use of $\tau_{ph}(E)$ in Eq. 8, to investigate the phonon heat transport. Numerical results of $\tau_{ph}(E)$ and κ_{ph} are plotted in Figs. 2(d-f) and 2(h) respectively. From the plots of $\tau_{ph}(E)$, it is evident that below Debye energy ($\hbar\omega_D$; the maximum energy a phonon can have), there exists a certain energy interval corresponding to which phonon modes are absent. The width of this energy interval (gap) is proportional to the mass difference of the constituent atoms. Accordingly, the gap is maximum (minimum) for the CuAu (CuAg) wire. These are the expected results, as two different atoms in this topology form a linear lattice consisting of diatomic basis. A comparison with pristine wires reveal that alloying decreases (increases) about 14% of the Debye energy of AgAu wire (Cu based bimetallic wires).

Figure 2: Different transport properties of CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu bimetallic atomic wires in linear topology: (a-c) electronic transmission coefficient τ_{el} plotted as a function of $(E-E_F)$; (d-f) phononic transmission coefficient τ_{ph} plotted as a function of phonon energy E ; (g-i) electronic κ_{el} , phononic κ_{ph} , and relative phononic thermal conductance κ_{ph}/κ , respectively, plotted as a function of temperature by taking chemical potential $\mu = 0$ eV.

Ladder Topology:Although T -dependence of G not plotted here, it found that, G is nearly independent ($\approx 2G_0$) of T for all bimetallic wires similar to pristine wires, and is just equal to its average value for constituent pristine wires. Interestingly, these results are in contrast with the corresponding finding for bimetallic wires in linear topology. The T independence of G is mainly a consequence of the smooth behavior of the $\tau_{el}(E)$ about E_F as shown in Figs. 4(a-c). Also, in magnitude, a significant enhancement in G is observed for all wires, with 57% at $T=300$ K in CuAu wire.

Figure 3 Electrical conductance G as a function of temperature for linear topology of CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu bimetallic atomic wires, respectively.

Figure 4: Different transport properties of CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu bimetallic atomic wires in ladder topology. The curves are labelled in the same way as in Fig. 2.

Like G , both κ_{el} and κ_{ph} also show an enhancement for all wires and this enhancement is about 32% and 60% at $T=300$ K, respectively, for CuAu wire. Obviously, it is due to the increased number of conduction channels for both electron and phonon transport as noted from Figs. 4(a-c) and 4(d-f), respectively. The enhancement in κ_{ph} is more pronounced, since in addition to increased channels, drastic contraction in phonon energy gap and increase in Debye energy causes enhancement in κ_{ph} . Figures 4(g-h) depict the temperature dependence of κ_{el} and κ_{ph} for different wires. Further, κ_{ph} (i) unlike to κ_{el} , exhibit a significantly varying wire dependent T behavior, (ii) follows qualitatively similar T -dependence with unchanged order as that for corresponding wire in linear topology. Also, the heat conduction for all wires is now dominated by the valence electrons over the investigated T , with CuAg wire having the maximum phononic contribution ($\sim 14\%$ at $T=300$ K). Recently, Belhadi and Khater [24] have reported a qualitatively similar behaviour of κ_{ph} for a related system of two coupled monatomic chains of Au.

Thermoelectric properties

The thermopower S and total thermoelectric figure of merit ZT is calculated using Eqs. (4) and (9). Further, their tunability via the chemical potential μ of the electrodes is also

explored as it can be changed through various means such as electrostatic or electrochemical gating or doping. Here, μ is varied from -2.0 eV to 2.0 eV, with respect to DFT Fermi level. The room-temperature results of $S(\mu)$ and $ZT(\mu)$ for wires in different topologies are depicted in Figs. 5(a-b) and 6(a-b), respectively.

Figure 5: Room-temperature thermopower S plotted as a function of chemical potential μ (measured with respect to the Fermi energy E_F) for different noble bimetallic wires in (a) linear, and (b) ladder topologies.

Thermopower:

Like pristine wires, S as a function of μ highly depends upon the topology and the type of bimetallic wire. Also it shows not only oscillatory but the sign change behavior. However, S now exhibit enhancement mainly near the $\mu = 0$ with maximum about 20 times found in AgAu linear wire as compared to the average of S for its constituents pristine wires in corresponding topology. This enhancement in S is originated from the change in electronic band structure as compared to pristine wires which leads to change in electronic transmission function entirely governed by projected density of states of bimetallic wires. Furthermore, S possess two pronounced peaks (positive and negative magnitude) symmetrical positioned about a particular μ (say μ_N) if electronic transmission function is zero in the energy range around μ_N . Moreover, the sign of S in this energy range is mainly decided by term $N_1(\mu, T)$, since $N_0(\mu, T)$ is always positive (see Eq. (4)). In fact, at $\mu = \mu_N$, the contributions in integral $N_1(\mu, T)$ from sub intervals $(-\infty, \mu)$ and (μ, ∞) are nearly equal and opposite which makes $S=0$. It means thermo-currents due to electrons and holes get compensated. However, for $\mu <(>)\mu_N$, S gets positive (negative) sign as the dominant contribution now comes from the sub-interval $-\infty(\infty)$ to μ . In this case thermo-current due to holes (electrons) dominates over electrons (holes), accordingly a negative (positive) voltage is needed to block the current. Then by definition of Seebeck, it becomes positive (negative). Interestingly, only CuAu wire in linear topology has positive $S \sim 17 \mu V$ at $\mu = 0$. Recently,

Total Figure of Merit ZT: From Figs. 6(a-b) it is noticed that like S , the figure of merit ZT also has a significant dependence on μ , the type of alloying, and the wire topology. Over the investigated range of μ , ZT shows a number of pronounced peaks located at characteristics values of μ . Like S , ZT also shows enhancement for each bimetallic wire with respect to its average value for constituent's pristine wires. For CuAg bimetallic wires in linear topology, this enhancement is maximum and is about 3 times. However, the two pronounced peaks about μ_N in S do not appeared in ZT due to extremely small G about μ_N ; instead these peaks shift toward the edges of the energy gap. Similar behavior of ZT has also been predicted in pristine wires of noble metals [17]. As κ_{ph} reduces with alloying and is appeared in denominator of Eq. (9), it is also one of the cause for enhancement in ZT . A quantitative analysis reveals that unlike S , ZT is almost zero at $\mu = 0$ for all bimetallic wires. Evangelini et al. [25] have also observed experimentally a similar sign change of S for metallic atomic-size contacts of Pt and Au at room temperature.

Figure 6: Room-temperature total figure of merit ZT plotted as a function of chemical potential μ (measured with respect to the Fermi energy E_F) for CuAg, CuAu, and AgAu bimetallic wires in (a) linear, and (b) ladder topologies.

Conclusion

In summary, we have carried out a systematic first principles theoretical study on electrical, thermal and thermoelectric transport properties of bimetallic atomic wires of

Cu, Ag, and Au noble metals. Two different topologies, viz. linear, and ladder, are considered. Both electronic and phononic contributions to thermal transport are calculated with the use DFT and GULP code, respectively, followed by Landauer-Büttiker approach based non-equilibrium Green's function method. As an important finding alloying has been found to introduce both qualitative and quantitative changes in the transport properties, with bimetallic wires having properties different from the average behavior of constituent pristine atomic wires. Notably, alloying brings (i) semiconducting behavior in most of the considered atomic wires with a sizeable energy band gap (ii) finite energy gap(s) in the phonon excitation spectra. We found a many-fold increase in the thermoelectric figure of merit ZT over the pristine wires, for instance AgAu wire in linear topology has the maximum $ZT \approx 3.3$ at $\mu = -0.6$ eV. This constitutes an important finding of our study from the point of view of generation of electric energy from heat energy. Our study predicts that $|S|$ as large as ~ 750 $\mu\text{V/K}$ can be achieved at $\mu = -0.1$ in the AgAu wire in linear configuration, suggesting its usefulness in thermal sensing applications.

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